

FISH BIODIVERSITY OF HARWA JABBAR JHEEL OF KATI HAR DISTRICT OF BIHAR

Mahalakshmi Kumari, M.Rauf Anwar

Department of Zoology, Purnea (PG) College, Purnea, Bihar, India

Abstract

Harwa Jabbar lake is a natural lake of about 300ha located in the Katihar district of Bihar. This lake gets attached through the river in the moon soon and become the main source of stocking of the fishes. The present study has been conducted to study the physico-chemical parameters of water and soil. The benthos and the fishes available in the lake has also been recorded.

Key word: Harwa jabbar lake, physico-chemical, fish diversity

INTRODUCTION

The Harwa Jabbar Jheel is a natural lake situated in the Aazamnagar block of Katihar district in Bihar. The lake gets connected with river Ganga during rainy season. It is used for both irrigation and fisheries purpose.

The lake has been selected for study of fish fauna in relation to Physico-chemical parameters and the fish culture activities in the lake. In a lake the macro benthic communities, invertebrate communities and fishes availability changes in response to changes in physico-chemical factors and available habitats. The biotic structure and water quality of streams and rivers reflect an integration of the physical, chemical and anthropogenic processes occurring in a catchment area, leading to the concept of ecological integrity. Human induced hydrological changes, physical disturbances (habitat alteration, urban land use) and point and nonpoint sources of pollution (chemical contamination, surface runoff, intensive agriculture) are examples of processes responsible for a broad-scale deterioration of lotic and lentic ecosystems. The abundance of benthic fauna greatly depends on physical and chemical properties of the substratum. Benthic macro-invertebrates can be used as a barometer of overall biodiversity in aquatic ecosystems and productivity.

Biological assessment and criteria can be used as the basis for management programs, restoring and maintaining the chemical, physical and biological integrity of freshwater. Live organisms offer valuable information regarding their surrounding conditions and can be used to evaluate the physical, chemical and biological impact and their cumulative effects (Karr and Chu, 1999). In addition, surveys of the richness and species composition, the relative abundance of groups or species and the feeding relationships between the inhabiting organisms are the most direct measure to determine if a water body meets the biological standards for aquatic life. Realising their immense importance, several workers have attempted to study the diversity of macro benthic invertebrates in aquatic ecosystem in lotic and lentic water bodies.

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The development of fisheries in these fresh water resources is the present need using scientific techniques. Limnological investigations on water bodies were generally analyzed to determine the pollution level of the water bodies time to time. The abiotic and biotic factors of the water influence the quality and quantity of aquatic life surviving there. The role of water in nature is unique not only for human; but, also for the numerous organisms living in the water. The physical and chemical properties of fresh water bodies are characterized by the climatic, geochemical, geo morphological and pollution condition. In order to utilize fresh water bodies successfully for fish production, it is very important to study the Physico-Chemical factors influencing the biological productivity in the water bodies (Sahni and Yadav, 2012). The quality of aquatic life surviving in the pond is totally dependent on the water quality of the pond.

According to Department of Fisheries, Govt. of Bihar North Bihar comprises 821 sq. kms. of wetland areas in the form of lakes (36548 ha), Oxbow lakes (4735 ha) and ponds and swamps (46800 ha) Pandey et al., (1998). There is wide range of fish biodiversity in the state; some work has been done to study the fish biodiversity of the state. The objective of present work is to study the fish fauna of the lake which is under capture and culture practices, its abiotic and biotic factors and the socioeconomic condition of fisherman dependent on the lake.

The Harwa Jabbar Jheel is a natural lake situated in the Azamnagar, Katihar district in Bihar at an latitude of 21°- 58'-10'' N~27° , 31°-15'' N and longitude of 82°-19°-50'' E. The lake gets connected with river Ganga during rainy season. It is used for both irrigation and fisheries purpose. An investigation has been conducted to study the physico-chemical parameters and fauna of the lake. The preliminary observation revealed that the lake is ecologically rich in planktonic flora and fish biodiversity. The objective of the present work is to study the abiotic and biotic profile of the pond, fish biodiversity and suitable measures to bring the water body for employment and income gain.

Location map of the pond under investigation

Materials and Methods

The Physico chemical parameters of all the ponds were monitored on monthly basis as per standard methology. The soil analysis was done on half yearly basis as per standard methodology (APHA, AWWA, WPCF, 1989). The following parameters was studied ;

- (1) Temperature

- (2) pH
- (3) Alkalinity
- (4) Free Carbon dioxide
- (5) Dissolved oxygen
- (6) Conductivity
- (7) Transparency
- (8) Biological oxygen demand (BOD)
- (9) Estimation of plankton
- (10) Estimation of soil pH
- (11) Estimation of Organic Carbon % in soil
- (12) Estimation of soil Nitrogen
- (13) Estimation of Soil Phosphorus
- (14) Estimation of Potassium in Soil

Collection of fishes:

Fish collection was made with the help of local fisherman and the catches of fishers. The fishing was done by using different mesh size gill net, cast net, trap and angling. After the collection of fish, the sampled specimens were immediately preserved in 10% formalin for identification.

Before preservation photograph was taken with the help of Nikon digital camera. The identification was made with the help of taxonomic references (Jhingran, 1975; Linderberg, 1976; Day, 1978; Srivastava, 1986; Talwar and Jhingran, 1991; Jayaram, 1999; Das et al., 2010).

Collection of benthos

The benthos was collected using the Ekman dredge from the different places. The organism collected was identified in the laboratory.

Collection of Plankton

The plankton was collected by filtering 50 litres of pond water from different places with plankton net and preserved in formalin for further study in the laboratory.

Results and Discussion

The soil analysis of pond is presented in the Table -1. The observation revealed that the pH was alkaline ranging from 7.1 to 8.0. The phosphorus ranges 11.2 mg/kg to 17.4mg/kg, potash 103mg/kg to 501mg/kg Nitrogen 520mg/kg to 978.1mg/kg. The organic carbon percentage was 2.1 to 4.0.

Table 1: Soil analysis of the pond

Pond soil	N (mg/kg)	P (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	O C%	pH
Average	739.9±22 9.5	14.5±3. 11	318±2 01	3.0±0. 95	7.5±0. 45

The physico chemical parameters of the three points recorded in table 2-6 represent that the air temperature ranges from 16.2 to 34.5⁰c. Whereas water temperature varied from 19.4 to 31.5⁰c. The pH of the water varied from 7.4 to 9.6. The dissolved oxygen concentration varied from 5.0 ppm to 9.8 ppm. The free carbon dioxide concentration was recorded 14 ppm to 22 ppm. The biological oxygen demand was 13.2 to 26.4 ppm. The total alkalinity varied from 188 ppm to 220 ppm. The conductivity varied from 2.1 to 2.82. The transparency varied from 28.0 cm to 35.7 cm and plankton concentration was 0.2 to 0.4ml.

Table:2 Physico-chemical parameters of the pond

Month	Air temp. (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (ppm)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton (ml)
October`11	24.5	21.0	7.6	6	20	202	2.82	36.0	14.8	0.3
November`11	26.7	17.2	7.5	6	22	216	2.74	33.2	15.8	0.3
December`11	24.2	22.4	7.4	6.4	20	210	2.60	32.6	16.2	0.4
Jan`12	19.4	16.2	7.6	8	16	196	2.3	29.5	19.2	0.3
Feb`12	21.6	18.4	7.6	7.6	20	190	2.34	30.5	19.4	0.4
March`12	25.2	24.5	7.9	6.4	14	180	2.4	30.1	20.2	0.4
April`12	27.5	29.5	8.2	6	10	188	2.5	29.5	23.8	0.4
May`12	34	31.0	8.5	5.6	8	188	2.66	29.2	25.8	0.3
June`12	34.5	30.5	8.6	5.6	8	186	2.68	29.	26.2	0.3
July`12	27	29.0	8.1	6.4	10	186	2.7	30.2	24.4	0.3
August`12	25.4	27.0	8.0	6	12	192	2.8	34.0	20.4	0.2
September`12	28.4	26.5	7.8	5.6	18	196	2.8	26.0	18.6	0.2

Table:3 Physico-chemical parameters of the pond

Month	Air temp. (⁰ C)	Water temp. (⁰ C)	pH	DO (ppm)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton (ml)
October`12	24.6	21.8	9.1	9.1	20	206	2.74	34.4	16.8	0.3
November`12	22.5	17.5	9.2	9.2	22	220	2.61	32	15.4	0.3
December`12	21.5	22.6	9.3	9.8	20	202	2.54	31.8	14.4	0.3
Jan`13	20.2	17	9.2	9.2	18	198	2.22	28.3	16.8	0.2
Feb`13	22.5	18	8.5	8.5	22	193	2.26	29.4	15.4	0.3
March`13	26.1	24.5	8.5	8.5	16	184	2.32	29.1	17.4	0.3
April`13	28.4	29	8.7	8.7	12	192	2.41	28.3	19.4	0.2
May`13	35.0	31.5	8.8	8.4	12	192	2.56	28	20.4	0.2
June`13	35.2	30.5	8.1	8.1	10	186	2.64	28.8	23.4	0.3
July`13	28.6	29.5	8.1	8.1	12	186	2.67	29.1	24.6	0.2
August`13	26.8	27.5	8.0	8.0	14	194	2.71	32.4	20.0	0.2
September13	25.5	26.8	7.8	7.8	18	199	2.70	34.1	20.2	0.2
Average	26.4	24.6	8.6±	8.6	16.3	196	2.5	30.4	18.6	0.25
	±4.8	±5.2	0.52	±0.6	±4.2	±10	± 0.18	±2.3	±3.2	±0.05

Table: 4 Relative abundance of Phytoplankton species recorded from the pond

	Phytoplankton species recorded from the ponds	Relative abundance
Chlorophyceae		
	Pandorina sp	+
	Ankistrodesmus sp	++
	Pediastrum sp.	+
	Spirogyra sp.	+
	Kirchneriella sp.	++
	Eudorina sp.	+
	Chlorella sp	+
	Closterium sp	++
	Scenedesmus sp	+
	Cosmarium sp.	++
Myxophyceae		
	Oscillatoria sp.	+
	Cylindrospermum sp	+
	Merismopedia sp	+
	Microcystis sp	++
	Spirulina sp.	+
	Anabaena sp.	++
	Phormidium sp.	+
Bacillariophyceae		
	Navicula sp.	+
	Surirella sp.	+
	Melosira sp.	+
	Cyclotella sp	+
	Nitzschia sp.	+
	Synedra sp.	+
	Fragilaria sp	+
	Asterionella sp.	+
	Stephanodiscus sp.	+
	Euglena sp.	+
	Phacus sp.	+

Table: 5 Relative abundance of Zooplankton species recorded from the pond

Sl.no	Zooplankton species recorded from the pond	Relative abundance
Protozoa		
1	Vorticella sp	+
2	Ceratium sp.	+
3	Peridinium sp.	-
Rotatoria		
1	Brachionus sp.	+
2	Keratella sp.	+
3	Filinia sp.	+
4	Asplanchna sp.	-
5	Polyarthra sp.	+
Lalodocera		
1	Moina sp.	++
2	Ceriodaphnia sp.	++
3	Chydorus sp.	++
4	Daphnia sp.	++
5	Bosmina sp..	++
Copepoda		
1	Mesocyclops sp	+
2	Microcyclops sp.	+
3	Heliodyptomus sp.	+

Table:6 Fish fauna of the Lake (January-December 2012)

Order	Family	Scientific Name	IUCN Status	Local Name
Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	<i>Labeo rohita</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Rohu
		<i>Labeo calbasu</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Basrahi
		<i>Labeo gonius</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Kursa
		<i>Puntius ticto</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Sidhari/Pothia
		<i>Puntius sophore</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Pothia
		<i>Puntius Sarana</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Darahi
		<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Naini
		<i>Cirrhina reba</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Rewa/Reba
		<i>Catla catla</i> (Hamilton)	VU	Bhakura/Catla
		<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> (Hamilton)		Dhawahi
		<i>Aspidoparia morar</i> (Hamilton)		Chilwa
Siluriformes	Bagridae	<i>Wallago attu</i> (Bloch & Schneider)	NT	Boyari
		<i>Ompak bimaculatus</i> (Bloch)	EN	Jalkapoor
		<i>Mystus aor</i> (Hamilton)	VU	Tengra
		<i>Mystus vittatus</i> (Bloch)	VU	Tengra
		<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> (Bloch)	VU	Singhi
		<i>Clarias batrachus</i> (Linnaeus)	VU	Mangur
		<i>Anabas testudineus</i> (Bloch)	VU	Kawai
		<i>Colisa fasciatus</i> (Bloch & Schneider)	NT	Kotra

		<i>Ambassis nama</i> (Hamilton)	NE	Chamwa
		<i>Ambassis ranga</i> (Hamilton)	NE	Chanari
		<i>Glossogobius giuris</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Bulla
Channiformes	Channidae	<i>Channa gachua</i> (Hamilton)	NE	Chanaga
		<i>Channa marulius</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Saur
		<i>Channa punctatus</i> (Bloch)	NT	Garai
		<i>Channa striatus</i> (Bloch)	NT	Sauri
Mastacembeliformes	Mastacembelidae	<i>Macrognathus aria</i> (Bloch & Schneider)	NT	Pateya
		<i>Macrognathus aculeatus</i> (Bloch)	NE	Gainchi
		<i>Notopterus notopterus</i> (Pallas)	NT	Bhuna/Patra
		<i>Notopterus chitala</i> (Hamilton)	EN	Moya
Beloniformes	Belontiidae	<i>Xenentodon cancila</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Kauwa
Symbranchiiformes	Amphiniidae	<i>Amphipnous cuchia</i> (Hamilton)	NE	Bami
Tetraodontiformes	Tetraodontidae	<i>Tetraodon Cutcutia</i> (Hamilton)	NT	Galphulani

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The pond under investigation is an old pond. The pond may be constructed with an idea to water harvest the rainwater for flood control which could be used for agricultural and domestic purposes. In the long run when population has increased the periphery of the water bodies has inhabited by dense population and releases the untreated waste in the water bodies leading to eutrophication of the pond, dense algal bloom etc. There is no scientific fish culture in the pond for economic and employment gain.

The present study was conducted to study the abiotic, biotic factor and the fish fauna available in the lake. The nutritional status of the pond soil i.e. pH (7.1-8.0) slightly alkaline. The value of soil Nitrogen (520.0-978.1mg/kg) Phosphorus 11.2-17.4mg/kg Potash (103-501mg/kg.) and organic carbon % of the pond (2.1- 4.08%) keeps the pond under productive categories. The air temperature of the area was, 26.4 ± 4.3 , water temperature 24.4 ± 5.3 pH of the water 7.9 ± 0.39 , Dissolved Oxygen 6.3 ± 0.76 , free carbondioxide, 14.8 ± 5.0 , Total alkalinity 194 ± 10.5 , Biological oxygen demand 20.4 ± 3.8 , conductivity 2.6 ± 0.18 and Plankton was 0.31 ± 0.07 recorded. Among the benthic organisms Annelida was maximum followed by insect and Mollusca.

Under Zooplankton population maximum number recoded was Lalodocera (31%) followed by Copepoda (19%) in phytoplankton population the Bacillariophyceae (42%) was maximum followed by Chlorophyceae (34%). The pond is under culture –cum- capture practice the total number of 33 species of fishes were recorded. The Cypriniformes had maximum contribution. On the basis of productivity of the pond some suggestions has been made so that it could be brought under full production for gainful employment and income.

pH is another important parameter affecting species diversity and distribution in an ecosystem. The pH value of the water in the present investigation was alkaline. The alkaline pH was found to be associated with more number of species. However, with increasing pH, the number of species has been reported to decrease (Venkateswarju, 1969).

Electrical conductivity and dissolved solids are directly proportional to each other (Mittal and Senger, 1989). As per Rawson (1960) criterion these ponds with electrical conductance well above 0.20 mS could be considered eutrophic. The observed inverse relationship of EC with depth of visibility may be due to higher amount of dissolved and suspended matter in the ponds. A close perusal to depth of visibility of ponds indicates that in general, occurrence of high algal biomass coincided with low clarity values. Sharma and Durve (1991) proposed a regional classification for assigning trophic status to water bodies using average Secchi disc values. On the basis of depth of visibility values these ponds could be categorized as 'moderately eutrophic'. One of the most important abiotic factors influencing life in aquatic ecosystem is the dissolved oxygen. Its depletion perhaps is the most critical manifestation of pollution. The dissolved oxygen content of the ponds was maximum in winter and minimum in monsoon during the present investigation. Patil and Panda (1986) recorded the dissolved oxygen content ranging from nil to the maximum of 3 mg/l in an organically polluted system. The overall variation in dissolved oxygen indicate critical levels of dissolved oxygen during the extreme summer period but the value increased in the subsequent period to attain super saturation by the end of June in the ponds . Phosphorus and nitrogen are the basic nutrients which are important to determine the productivity of lakes. The nitrogen, phosphorus, potash and organic

carbon value of the soil indicates that the ponds are under productive group. The alkalinity of the ponds water was in favourable range. The plankton concentration (qualitative estimation) especially the zooplankton was low may be due to high consumer of zooplankton or poor production may be due to more organic carbon load. Although it was found that Lalodocera > Rotatoria > Copepods > Protozoans. Among Phytoplanktons the concentration was Bacillariophyceae > Chlorophyceae > Myxophyceae.

The analysis of adverse affect of sewage on the structure of communities of aquatic organisms was among the first environmental assessment methods popularly adopted. Those organisms are able to tolerate sewage discharge were categorized as saprobic, those that could only survive in relatively pristine conditions were labeled as oligotrophic and those somewhere in between were known mesotrophic. Ample evidence exists that the macro-benthic community acts as a bio-indicator and has become a very important biological tool for the assessment of water quality (Hynes, 1965; Sinha and Das, 1993 and Kumar, 1997). From the results of present study it is clearly evident that the macro-benthic community is dominated by *Chironmus* larvae population in the ponds. The availability and distribution of chironomids on intra lake level have been attributed to be relative to many factors (Bowman, 1976). *Chironomus* larvae have also been used as pollution indicators by number of workers (Gaufin, 1957; Curry, 1962). Thus, the abundance of chironomids in the benthic population is due to impact of altered nature of substrate due to organic pollution. The presence of *Tubifex* sp., *Limnodrilus* sp. and *Limnaea accuminata* in lake also corroborates with the work of Mason (1981). Answar and Siddiqui (1988) recorded summer peak abundance of benthic invertebrates. From the present investigation, it is inferred that littoral benthic macro-invertebrate community can be useful in evaluating the localized effects of organic enrichment in the lentic systems whereas profundal benthos indicate the water quality as a whole (Mastrantuono, 1986).

The ponds are not under full exploitation of fish culture though it has got potentiality and can bring the income and employment in the area through fish culture. The fish species may stocked as per the primary productivity of the pond for better utilization which will also improve the water quality.

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